

CONCEPTIONEERING AND MASTER PLANNING OF BANKURA MULTI-VILLAGE WATER SUPPLY PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

Bankura is one of the districts in the state of West Bengal, where the villages have no water supply network. This paper describes the master planning of water supply scheme for about 600 villages and 4000 km of network length. The challenges included highly undulated terrain, transients, DMA demarcation, pressure management etc. With modelling of 108 pumps, mass balancing of 66 reservoirs and analysing the network in more than 50 scenarios, the scheme is successfully designed for 24X7 water supply and minimum 12 m of residual pressures. The network can serve a peak design demand of 257 MLD by conjunctive use of ground and surface water. 208 km of rising main network is analysed for transients and surge protection devices are proposed to ensure network safety. The project pioneers DMA demarcation in rural water supply network. Better water management and equitable water supply can be achieved by DMA operations. Pressure reducing valves are used to dynamically manage the pressures. The project aims to restrict NRW to less than 15% by dynamic pressure management. The isolation valves are placed critically in the network. These can be later used for detection of leakages in the network. With use of advance tools in WaterGEMS, Python programming, 60% of the design time is saved. The model is integrable with SCADA and utility's HMI for making better decisions during operations. The scheme is designed for 30 years and benefits about 1 million residents of 4 blocks in Bankura district.

Keywords: *Rural water supply, Hydraulic modelling, DMA demarcation, Dynamic Pressure Management System*

1. INTRODUCTION

Drinking water is one of the basic needs of life and essential for survival. More than one billion people all over the world do not have ready access to an adequate and safe water supply and more than 800 million of those are from rural areas. In India, ground water is being used as raw water for 85% public water supply (world health report,1998). The natural sources of water supply are contaminated with pathogenic agents, chemicals, heavy metals, pesticides water disinfectants and their byproducts as a consequence of industrial and agricultural activities leaching from soil, rocks, and atmospheric deposition and other human activities has become a hazard to human health in several parts of India. People living in these areas are always prone to occurrence of different water borne diseases. In addition to this, Indian women take up to six trips a day to gather and transport water. In rural areas the walk can be as long as average 10 miles a day carrying up to 15 litres in each trip (<https://thewaterproject.org>).

Considering the current situation, there is a need of paradigm shift. The Department of Drinking Water and Sanitation of Government of India provides technical and financial assistance to the States to provide safe and adequate drinking water to rural India. The Department's Centrally Sponsored Scheme, the National Rural Drinking Water Programme (NRDWP), currently focuses on providing access to drinking water to India's rural population. The Department is committed to provide household piped water supply to all rural households by 2024 with a focus on small scale, community managed schemes, groundwater schemes wherever possible, with emphasis on source sustainability through groundwater recharge and wastewater reuse (<https://jalshakti-ddws.gov.in>).

West Bengal is one of the states of India which has received funds from Asian Development Bank for execution of multivillage bulk water supply project with the support of Public health and Engineering Department. The project consists of development of efficient pipe distribution network in rural areas of West Bengal. Pressure management and reduction of water losses from the existing system are the two challenges in front of the management. Traditional approaches are insufficient to tackle this two-fold problem. Therefore, advanced techniques of modelling, designing and optimisation of the water distribution network needs to be developed and utilised to efficiently manage the available water.

Analysis and design of pipe network create a relatively complex problem, particularly if the network consists of range of pipes. Many methods have been tried in the past to compute the flows in the network of pipes which ranges from graphical methods to the use of physical analogies and finally to the use of mathematical models (G. Venkataramana, 2015). In the present study, reliability of the water distribution system can be computed by carrying out hydraulic simulation using Bentley's WaterGEMS.

1.1 Study area and data

Bankura the administrative unit of West Bengal state of India is chosen as the study area. It is a part of Medinipur division—one of the five administrative divisions of West Bengal. The District of Bankura is divided in eight blocks. Damodar River flows in the northern part of Bankura district and separates it with the major part of Burdwan district. The district head quarter is in Bankura town. The district has been described as the "connecting link between the plains of Bengal on the east and Chota Nagpur plateau on the west." The areas to the east and north-east are low-lying alluvial plains while to the west the surface gradually rises with rocky hillocks.

Bankura is one of the districts of West Bengal where no habitation has piped drinking water supply. The villagers cater to their daily water demand from unreliable wells, lakes, streams, ponds, public bore wells etc. The ground water sources are contaminated with fluoride and arsenic with arsenic concentration as high as 9 mg/lit. As a result, the Public Health and Environmental Engineering Department (PHED) of West Bengal has selected Bankura for Multi-Village Bulk Water Supply Project jointly funded by PHED and ADB (Asian Development Bank). The study area was limited

to automated hydraulic modelling and design of rural water supply scheme for four blocks of **Bankura district** namely Joypur, Sonamukhi, Patrasayer and Kotulpur covering an area of 1216 sqKm. Geographical Location of Bankura district can be found in Fig.1

Figure 1. Geographical Location of Bankura district

The census data required for the project was supplied by Public Health and Environmental Engineering Department of West Bengal and aerial survey data was obtained from Srijan Ecological Upliftment, Pvt. Ltd, Kolkata (<https://www.zaubacorp.com/company/SRIJAN-ECOLOGICAL-UPLIFTMENT-PRIVATE-LIMITED>). Hydraulic design and modelling for Bankura Rural Water Supply scheme was carried out using census and aerial survey data according to the specifications as mentioned in the Central Public Health and Environmental Engineering Organization Manual on Water Supply and Treatment, 1999 (<http://cpheeo.gov.in>).

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Background

There are about 7,00,000 residents living in 1,51,000 households spread across 655 villages of four blocks (Joypur, Sonamukhi, Patrasayer and Kotulpur) of Bankura district. Villagers face acute water shortage and have huge impact on their health as the ground water sources are contaminated with fluoride and arsenic. As per the BIS Standard for drinking water (BIS 1991 and subsequent modifications), the maximum permissible limit of Arsenic concentration in ground water is $10\mu\text{g/L}$ and for fluoride it is $1.5\mu\text{g/L}$. In India arsenic concentration had been found to be widespread in different region of the West Bengal due to dissolution of arsenic containing bed rocks.

Arsenic is highly toxic and long-term use of drinking water with high concentrations can lead to a wide range of health problems in humans. Arsenic is carcinogenic, mutagenic, and teratogenic. Symptoms of chronic arsenicosis include skin lesions such as melanosis and keratosis, and skin cancer. Whereas the most prevalent health problem related to chronic exposure of fluoride from drinking water are dental or skeletal fluorosis (<http://www.adb.org>). Unfortunately, one of the blocks of study area records the fluoride concentration as high as 9mg/L . As a result, reorganization and master planning of entire scheme from Intake wells to individual households became an essential task.

In this project about 4,000 km of additional raw water rising mains, clear water rising/ gravity mains and distribution network, put together, is proposed. Optimization of Pipes layout wherever

necessary has been done. Parallel rider mains have been provided for larger pipes to avoid puncturing at numerous locations on larger pipes.

2.2 Scope of the Work

The objective of the study includes, master planning, hydraulic modelling and designing of the pumping mains and distribution network up to individual households which can be achieved through the development of a digital water distribution network model using GIS enabled and Hydraulically intelligent Infrastructure.

Owing to complex topology of project area, the scope of the work was finalized as:

- Detailed UAV based topographical survey of all roads in all 4 blocks
- Hydraulic Modelling of Distribution and Transmission mains from Sources i.e. from 66 Tube Wells from the basin of Dwarkeshwar River to OHRs in Joypur and Kotulpur blocks and from One Intake well at Damodar River to OHRs in Sonamukhi and Patrasayer blocks via WTP.
- From Ground level service reservoirs (GLSRs), independent clear water transmission lines shall feed multiple Overhead Reservoirs (OHSR/ ESR) in the project area.

Around 66 such ESR locations have been identified and 270 MLD of water shall be distributed under gravity from these ESRs. Sluice Valves, PRVs, Air Valves, Scour Valves, other pumping machineries, etc. had to be used in the scheme wherever required.

With successful completion of this project it is expected that all villagers shall get access to clean continuous good quality drinking water supply with adequate pressures and in equitable quantity. The standard of living of about 1.2 Million villagers is projected to improve drastically. Women who previously had to walk for long distances to fetch water would be saved from this trouble. puncturing at numerous locations on larger pipes.

2.3 Analysis of water distribution networks

Water distribution system consists of network elements viz. pipes, valves, tanks, reservoirs, pumps etc. While designing a new water distribution network or in expanding the existing one, it is essential to ensure continuous supply of potable water to the end user with enough pressure. Computation of pressure and flow in a complex network of pipes is a tedious but interesting task especially for those involved in design, construction and maintenance of the public water distribution system (G. VenketaRamana et al; 2015).

One of the earliest theories into finding solution to water flow and pressure in water distribution network includes the popular Hardy Cross method which is based on moment distribution theory. This is an iterative method for determining the flow in pipe network systems where the inputs and outputs are known, but the flow inside the network is unknown. The method was later replaced by computer algorithms employed for obtaining the solution to the problem either by Newton-Raphson method or other numerical methods that removed the need to solve nonlinear systems of equations manually.

Analysis and design of pipe networks is a complex problem, particularly if the network consists of range of pipes. The behaviour of a water distribution network can be determined by a sequence of steady state conditions, which form a small but vital component for assessing the adequacy of a network (Marino Castro Gama et al; 2017). Such an analysis is needed each time changing pattern of consumption or delivery are significant or, added features such as supplying of water, addition of booster pumps, pressure regulating valves or storage tanks, change the system. Many methods have been used in the past to compute flows in network of pipes such methods range from graphical methods to the use of physical analogies and finally to the use of mathematical models (IS standards,2012). These methods of network analysis have been developed and implemented on the computer over the last fifty years. One such method is a Hardy Cross Method. It was observed that the method converges very slowly or not at all which leads to suggest special measures to improve convergence and a constrained model for the minimum cost design of water distribution networks. Further this methodology attempted to account for the uncertainties in required demands, required pressure heads and pipe roughness coefficients. It was formulated an optimization problem as a non-

linear programming model which is solved using a generalized reduced gradient method. It shows that uncertainties in future demands, pressure head requirements, and pipe roughness can have significant effects on the optimal design and cost. Further the reliability of water distribution system can be computed by treating the demand, pressure head, and pipe roughness as random variables. It can also be assumed that water demand and pipe roughness coefficient follow a probability distribution, and then used a random number generator to generate the values of random variables for each node and pipe. It leads to hydraulic simulation and computed the pressure heads at the demand nodes, provided the demands are satisfied. Finally, nodal and system hydraulic reliabilities can be computed using Bentley's WaterGEMS (www.bentley.com , 2019)

3. EXPERIMENTATION USING WATERGEMS

Designing efficient water network with the object of reduction of physical water losses plays an important role in improving efficiency of water supply system. This is a challenging task which can be accomplished using automation. In the present study about 4000km of water distribution network for Bankura village has been developed and analysed using Bentley's WaterGEMS software. WaterGEMS is developed by Bentley systems, US. It has capacity to analyse unlimited number of pipes and tanks. WaterGEMS is a popular tool in analysing complex and simple water distribution networks. It performs extended period simulation of hydraulic behaviour within pressurised pipe networks. It is a tool for improving the user's understanding of the movement and fate of drinking water constituents within distribution systems. (www.bentley.com , 2019). In the present study, WaterGEMS has been used to carry out the hydraulic analysis of the distribution network of the study area.

Data pertaining to existing pipe network and roadmaps for proposed network was available in GIS. Hydraulic model was created using this database with the help of Model Builder tool of Bentley's WaterGEMS. The next step of elevation allocation from shapefile to nearly 50000 junctions was carried out using TRex tool with precision. Village wise /habitations wise population and density data for present, intermediate and ultimate year was used to allocate junction demands using area-based load allocation method inside Load Builder.

As per Central Public Health and Environmental Engineering Organization (CPHEEO Manual, 1999) demands are to be subjected to a Peak Factor 3 for zone population less than 50,000 souls. This was done using Demand Adjustments feature in calculation options. With Model Builder, TRex and Load Builder the entire process of initial model development was successfully completed. Connectivity errors in the initial model were removed using Network Navigator.

With Model Builder, TRex and Load Builder, entire process of initial model development was accomplished. Network Navigator was used to effectively remove all errors in model which was first built. Shared User Data Extension (UDX) attributes were created common for all elements including- 'DMA', 'Village Name', 'Gram Panchayat' etc. Quick creation of UDX allowed us to include 'additional' data from GIS inside WaterGEMS and it helped in decision making while designing.

Zones were reorganized and structured such that all junctions would get a minimum residual pressure of 12m of water for effective 24x7 supply. Different possible scenarios were evaluated for every zone with help of local constraint-based design in Darwin Designer tool, making it hydraulically reliable and sustainable. Dedicated Active Topology alternative was used for every Zone and DMA. Alternatives were created for different zonal demands over base, intermediate and ultimate years and for valves setting for operations.

Direct feeders were provided as per IWA and AWWA Guidelines to individual DMAs (<https://iwa-network.org> & <https://www.awwa.org>). Interconnections between two DMAs were provided through closed (but openable, if required) Isolation Valves for water supply emergencies during operations. The number and location of tanks, their capacities and staging heights were fixed considering different factors like land availability etc.

Pressure Release Valves (PRVs) were installed at the mouth of every DMA with proper controls for Dynamic Pressure Management Systems (DPMS) during operations. Optimization of number of Isolation Valves and fixing the locations of PRVs was possible with Criticality Analysis and for

strategizing isolation step test studies and understanding the critical segments. This exercise would be helpful to carry out leakage detection studies with the help of isolation step test. Separate report was prepared for such studies with segments color coded differently. The ‘export to zip’ option in WaterGEMS Connect Edition helped in quick data sharing with the government authorities enabling us to export the supporting background files along with the hydraulic model. It was mandatory to update the GIS database time to time with the changes to the hydraulic model. Model builder’s to and fro synchronization option helped in updating GIS database.

Changes in transmission routes, evaluating different options and finalizing few was challenging as the topology was greatly undulated and the habitations were sparsely located. This became possible with Scenarios Management using Active Topology Alternative. Optimal scheduling of pumping operations was essential as this project includes heavy pumping at different levels daily; extending from Intake structures/ Tube Wells to OHRs (Overhead Reservoirs). Energy to Cost calculations had to be done to understand the Wire-to-Water efficiency of more than 108 Pumps.

The tariff calculations and energy consumption studies were done on the hydraulic model using ‘Scenario Energy Cost’ tool. Mass Balancing of ESRs using EPS Calculation option-controlled tank levels thus prevention from overflowing or emptying. WaterGEMS facility of exporting excel reports in one click, generating inventory reports, profiles, etc. saved a lot of time.

3.1 DTK’s Software Customization :

In the previous assignment of modelling & designing our team felt a dire need of simple yet very powerful customizations and additions to WaterGEMS and associated work process. We could develop intelligent time saving solutions on the top of existing features of WaterGEMS. DTK created multiple small tools to carry out otherwise time-consuming activities. With Bentley’s WaterObjects.NET we created “Auto Re-labeler” feature- that relabels ALL the elements in A SINGLE WINDOW; “Auto Profile Publisher” feature- that automatically fetches profile data from WaterGEMS and publishes it on GIS Maps (Refer Fig. No.2-5). These are our baby-steps, but it saves a huge amount of TIME while dealing with such mega Water Projects. This possibly is the FIRST EVER ATTEMPT to the author’s notice of USING WATEROBJECTS.NET for WATERGEMS on Projects in INDIAN SUBCONTINENT.

Figure 2 Auto Re-Labeler

Figure 3 Ortho images from Drone Survey

Figure 4 Profile generated from Profile publisher

Figure 5 Profile publisher tool

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Using Bentley's WaterGEMS numerous design options were evaluated to arrive at an optimal design and operational strategies. The assignment was successfully completed in a period of 60 days which was almost one third of the anticipated time for this assignment.

All the design standards as specified by Central Public Health and Environmental Engineering Organization (CPHEEO) of Government of India for Rural Water Supply Schemes were followed and successfully achieved using WaterGEMS. It intelligently handled the complex and cliché design constraints and helped in delivery of appreciable outcomes in terms of time investment, increased monetary savings and improvements in living standard of nearly a million souls. The evaluation of worst-case scenarios, high demand factors, pressure zone management, etc. from WaterGEMS enabled detailed analysis of various "what if" operational scenarios has been carried out, This study would help the Public Health and Environmental Engineering Dept. of West-Bengal for optimally scheduling of operations; thus, improving the reliability of scheme.

It is observed that for various already commissioned projects in India, ESRs fail owing to overflowing and emptying issues. This results in a huge loss of capital investment and an under-utilization of scheme. In the present study this issue is addressed by carrying out the analysis and evaluation of operational strategies to avoid any such occurrence in the scheme by doing mass balancing of ESRs considering additional storage for emergency responses and increase in demands. Water management strategies were intelligently articulated with the use of FCVs, PRVs, Isolation Valves, TCVs and other valves while modelling. Settings on the valves were fixed based on pumping schedules and other electricity and water availability considerations.

The client appreciated our streamlined efforts in developing and improved designing of such huge hydraulic model. WaterGEMS helped our team to improve the productivity and enabled us to provide 'Out of Box' Solutions like smart pressure and water management, smart operations with implementation of concepts like DMAs (District metered areas) in Rural Scenarios. Total of 370+ DMAs were formed in 64 Distribution Zones.

In doing so, Hydraulic reliability and sustainability of network was achieved. We were able to seamlessly integrate with GIS Applications that were procured at client offices to cater for Base, Intermediate and Design year Water Demand mitigating all the challenges involved in execution of the assignment and meeting the specifications given by the client. With availability of DMA wise, Zone wise and total hydraulic model inventory reports through WaterGEMS, contractor will be able to

- Plan execution of the project with respect to Men, Machines, Materials and Money requirements.
- Plan order and delivery schedules of Inventory Items such as pipes, different types of valves, end caps for manufacturers/suppliers to have minimum carrying and storage costs of Inventory.
- Reconcile the inventory items as $\text{Balance Stock} = \text{Received Stock} - \text{Issued (Consumed) Stock}$.

Further through DMAs demarcation the govt. dept. is expected to carry out Water Auditing and control Water Leakages and thus restricting total NRW to less than 15%. The various shapefiles generated by WaterGEMS like Junctions, Pipes, etc. could be directly used to generate 350+ A0 sized Cutsheet Construction Drawings in LESS THAN 2 MAN DAYS. These drawings are required for utility's records and tendering and execution of project. The best part was each drawing carried inventory table and L-Section Profile of Network from WaterGEMS for every DMA/Zone, which would become very handy for departmental staff for deciding the quantity of various materials (pipes, valves, pumps, etc.) in tender and field engineers of the probable contractor to order material requirement from stores.

Bing Map feature in WaterGEMS helped to put background road maps/key landmarks on model instead of huge aerial imagery which prove to be of great help during designing and even executing the project. The project, when fully implemented, will directly improve the living standard of more than 1,200,000 people till the design year 2050 as potable drinking water will directly reach their doorsteps, giving them a sense of belonging and respite from daily worries of fetching water from wells, rivers, lakes and ponds etc. This would be a complete 180 degrees transformation of the existing situation.

Since the network is spread over a vast area, it is planned by the utility to procure SCADA for operational benefits and assistance for inaccessible areas. Our model provides an efficient foundation for utility to integrate hydraulic model with SCADA OPC Servers to get more precise operational insights in future. We are expecting successful implementation of such integration and it would be the first ever case of integration of SCADA with Hydraulic Models to the author's notice for any rural water supply network in India.

This streamlined our efforts and saved valuable time. Based on our earlier experience and complexity, we had projected to complete this assignment in 150 days' time. But with WaterGEMS, we could complete it in just 60 Days resulting in about 55% saving in Designing/ Modelling Costs.

4.1 DTK's Innovation

DTK Hydronet solution has contributed in this project by innovatively using the tool WaterGEMS Which can be described as under

4.1.1 Digital Twins:

All the assets in this Water Supply project are digitized, geo-referenced and meta data of various assets have been developed on GIS Application. Direct connection of this GIS Interface with Hydraulic Model allows to and fro communication and exchange of information and data that can be evolved as insights and dashboards. The performance modelling of the network using WaterGEMS EPS Scenarios allow users/ utility engineers to interpret the "what-if" condition results to take informed decisions and sustainably operate the network throughout its lifecycle. iModels have been developed from WaterGEMS to share this intelligence to handheld devices for ease during construction. The field intelligence from ground staff can then be marked on the iModels and can be sent back to GIS. Thus, maintaining and updating this digital twin of water network is possible and feasible in this project even during construction and O&M phases.

4.1.2 Digital Workflows:

Right from start to construction (and beyond) digital engineering workflows have been followed. Aerial images were used to develop an ortho-mosaic image, and geo-referencing, digitization of land cover/use, development of accurate terrain models was done in GIS. This GIS Data was then sent to WaterGEMS to model, analyze and design the water network. WaterGEMS allows complete integration with GIS allowing the utility to periodically update the models with field data observations on laid assets and update the models with pressure and flow observations for calibration activity.

4.1.3 Digital Context:

Since 'normal' as well as 'oblique' aerial imagery was captured using drones, digital terrain models and triangulation mesh were developed in GIS environment. This information was perhaps used to primarily extract contours for the design of Water network. However, it is proposed to the utility that use of these 3D models and images should also be extended to create a digital context of the area in alignment with not only the water network infrastructure but also other utility infrastructures like roads, etc.

4.1.4 Conceptioneering:

Since this project considers a wide scope of network modelling and designing of pipelines right from various water intake sources to numerous habitations through pumping and under gravity; a detailed analysis and comparison of every possible design and planning alternative had to be evaluated. Our team successfully did this with the virtue of hundreds of Scenarios and Alternatives. We used a dedicated Active Topology, Operational, Demand, Physical alternatives for every Zone and Sub-Zone. Alternatives were created and evaluated for different operational settings on valves, different zonal demands over base, intermediate and ultimate years, etc. Master planning was done within optimal time, with great considerations for savings for energy consumption, reduction in

overall carbon footprints and reduction in capital as well as operational costs for pumping machineries. We could save a huge amount of capital with the use of GIS and Active topology alternative to evaluate different routing options for transmission mains within single hydraulic model. Scenario results and Alerts function were used for comparisons of different hydraulic properties to check the overall model for violation of engineering compliance, if any. The evaluation of worst-case scenarios, high demand factors, dynamic pressure zone management, etc. from WaterGEMS enabled detailed analysis of various “what if” operational scenarios. This will help the PHED, West Bengal to schedule optimal and effective operations; thus, improving the overall reliability of the scheme. Inheritance in Scenarios helped in sub-categorizing child scenarios with inherited data from parent scenario. This saved huge time as we didn’t have to create ‘n’ number of models with ‘n’ number of inputs for every possible case. The conceptual design of distribution system conformed to all the specifications given by the client in terms of – Minimum Pressure, Maximum Velocity, Maximum Hydraulic Gradient, Peak Factor, Hazen-William’s Constant (C-Values) for pipes of various materials, Max-Day Demand for the design year 2050, Provision of DMAs based on international guidelines, Sluice Valves, PRVs and Scour Valves, Provision of interconnections between two DMAs, providing segmentations within a DMA using Criticality Analysis, for carrying out Step Test, wherever required, providing Bulk Meters at Tanks’ Outlets and at the entry of each DMA for measurement of NRW, etc.

Since, this project has completed its ‘Design’ stage at present, other innovations like Constructioneering, Inspectioneering and Operationeering do not apply to it. However, it is planned to integrate the hydraulic model to SCADA OPC Servers as well as operator’s HMI in the future after construction and commission. This would assist the utility to intelligently operate by consuming engineering results from WaterGEMS to predict the near future possibilities. SCADAConnect tool would be useful then to carry out quick ‘on the fly’ emergency breakdown scenarios to throw the model results back to HMI for operator’s understanding.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Permanent access to safe and sustainable water sources especially in rural areas is a major concern all over the world. An attempt has been made in this study to design a water distribution network for four blocks of Bankura district of West Bengal state of India. Automated hydraulic model has been developed for about 4000km of network length and evaluated using brilliant features of Bentley’s WaterGEMS. The hydraulic modelling is an effective way of mitigating the problem of water scarcity and improving the efficiency of water distribution network. The network is analysed and optimised for various possible scenarios so as to ensure reliability and sustainability during operation. DTK Hydronet solutions have developed custom built programs viz. “Auto Re- Labeller”, “Auto Profile publisher” using WaterObjects.net on top of WaterGEMS. This is the first attempt ever in India to the author’s notice which helped in saving time and cost. Innovative approach of digital workflow, digital twins, digital context and conceptioneering as adapted by DTK helped in more detailed evaluation of the project. In addition to this, mass balancing of ESR’s has been carried out to evaluate operational strategies so as to optimally schedule the operations and avoid overflowing. 370 plus DMA’s were formed in 64 Distribution zones considering the principle of smart pressure and water arrangements. Effective water auditing and water leakage control can be achieved through DMA demarcation. Various reports generated through the software can serve as a guideline to contractors to successfully plan and implement the execution of the project.

Since the network is spread over a vast area, it is planned by the utility to procure SCADA technology in the scheme for operational benefits and assistance for inaccessible areas. Our model provides an efficient foundation for the utility to integrate the hydraulic model with SCADA OPC servers to get more precise operational insights in future. The study expects a successful implementation of such integration that would be the first ever case of integration of SCADA with Hydraulic Models to the author’s notice for rural water supply network in India.

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